

Speculation on the Role of Velocity in Quantum Mechanics

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Velocity plays a central role in classical mechanics, yet quantum mechanics deals with the variables E, t, p and x . P nonrelativistically is $m_0 v$, but a given p value corresponds to various $m_1 v_1 = m_2 v_2 = m_3 v_3$ and so does not determine v uniquely. (A p, E pair or a p, m_0 pair is needed for this.). Here we consider a quantum particle in a square well potential. If detection of a particle occurs through impulse = Integral $F dt$, then $m_1 v_1 = p$ and $m_2 v_2 = p$ yield the same impulse although the velocities may be completely different. If one seeks a "time-independent" scenario then one would expect the two to yield the same spatial probability distribution even though E is different for each. In such a case E_1 and E_2 distinguish between v_1 and v_2 . For a particle in an infinite well v_1 and v_2 represent different frequencies and so this "frequency" information role is taken on by energy.

What happens if one considers two different average momenta levels for the same single particle? In such a case m_0 is fixed and p_1 and p_2 correspond to different v_1 and v_2 i.e. to different frequencies. There is no time in a time-independent scenario so how does one represent the relative frequencies? One may do this spatially, we argue. If $p_1 = n_1 \cdot 3.14/L$ and $p_2 = n_2 \cdot 3.14/L$ where L is the well size then p_1 has n_1 crests and p_2 , n_2 crests. Thus in one case relative velocity for the same p is distinguished by E_1 and E_2 , but not by any spatial distribution. In the second for the same m_0 and different v_1 and v_2 , there is both a different spatial distribution describing the relative frequencies, but also different E 's which also distinguish and are linked to frequency. This leads to the idea of probability crests with certain base widths proportional to $1/p$.

What happens in the case of a free particle? Such a particle should also be associated with crests linked to $1/p$, but the particle is traveling through space. It is not restricted to L and so its probability density should mimic classical mechanics i.e. be a constant everywhere. To allow for this one considers a probability distribution of crests and troughs together with a second spatially shifted distribution indicating the direction and nature motion, but with the constraint that the modulus is 1. This suggests $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ for the two distributions.

This is very different from the classical mechanical scenario of a bound state spatial density (1) which is proportional to dt with fixed dx i.e. $C dx/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity. Such a picture only accounts for relative densities in space. Thus for two different constant velocities v_1 and v_2 which represent different frequencies of traversing a distance L , the spatial density is the same classically. Thus important information is lost and we argue that $C dx/v(x)$ is incomplete. In quantum mechanics the envelope of $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)dx$ approaches the classical value for high n (energy level), but quantum mechanics contains much more information, namely the idea that different v for the same m_0 have different frequencies which must be manifested spatially.

Velocity in a Box

Classically velocity is essential in dynamics as a particle is described by $x(t)$ This notion should not be completely dropped in quantum mechanics. Consider a well of length L with infinite potential walls. The time-independent quantum wavefunction is $W(x) = C(L) \sin(px)$ where $p = n$

$3.14/L$ and the energy is $pp/2m$. Thus the spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ depends only on p i.e. there is a lack of information because $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2=m_3v_3$ etc are all solutions. What differentiates these is E_n which is $pp/2m$. E_n , however, appears in the wavefunction as $\exp(-iE_n t)$ and so has no impact on the spatial density. Thus two very different velocities and masses may yield the same p , but different energies. Because the velocities are different and the particle is restricted to a fixed L , v_1 and v_2 represent different frequencies. A single impulse is proportional to p , but the particle with a faster velocity has a higher frequency and delivers more impulse hits to the wall i.e. pressure is linked to E (kinetic energy) and not simply impulse. These are only distinguished by energy which thus is linked to frequency. Spatially for a time-independent probability distribution, there is no distinguishing the two classically very different pictures. This is not altogether disturbing because classically density is given by $C/v(x) dx$. For $v(x)=\text{constant}$ one has $1/L dx = \text{density}(x)$. Thus the normalized density really picks out relative velocities within L . A system with $m_1v_1=p$ and one with $p=m_2v_2$ would have the same spatial density i.e. a constant. In quantum mechanics the density is not a constant, but it does not distinguish between velocities for the same p . Nevertheless there is something incomplete about this picture if an impulse is able to distinguish frequencies as is discussed in the following section.

Same Rest Mass, Different Velocities

In the case of two different p solutions i.e. $p_1=n_1 3.14/L$ and $p_2/n_2 3.14/L$ with the same m_0 there are two different velocities and frequencies of motion. E_1 and E_2 are different and are linked with these frequencies, but now the spatial system should also distinguish between the two because they have different impulses. Thus the notion of different frequencies should appear in a time-independent spatial density scenario as well. How can this happen? P_1 delivers an impulse proportional to n_1 and has a velocity v_1 proportional to n_1 while p_2 delivers an impulse proportional to n_2 and has a velocity v_2 proportional to n_2 . The relative frequencies are $v_1/v_2 = n_2/n_1$. Thus having n_1 crests appear in L (i.e. space) for p_1 and n_2 crests for p_2 solves the problem. Increased frequency means more crests appearing in L . Unlike the same p different v situation, now two different p 's with different v 's and the same mass requires a visible frequency difference spatially, not just an increased energy/pressure.

Free Particle

How may these ideas be associated with a free particle? In the above section it was argued that for a given m_0 and p there should be crests with a base width proportional to $1/p$ representing a kind of spatial density. Thus there is spatial resolution even though the particle may be considered to be a point with momentum p . As a result one may have a repeated set of crests. These would describe a static (time-independent) density. A free particle is not subject to any boundary conditions (unlike the particle in the infinite well whose spatial density should vanish at the walls). Thus there seems to be a problem in choosing what point of the crest corresponds to $x=0$. Somehow a free particle should be linked to a constant spatial probability in all of space. This seems to be at odds with a finite width crest system. A second problem is that a set of crests or even a set of crests and troughs does not distinguish between motion to the

left or right (constant v), but these are different. A way to resolve this issue is to have two sets of probabilities. $P(x)=\text{constant}$ as in classical physics, but shows no dynamics. To bring in motion one may do the following. Instead of having a series of crests, one may use repeated crest troughs proportional to $1/p$. These show wavelike motion, but do not indicate whether the particle is moving to the right or left. To show directional motion, one needs two such sets to show how the distribution changes in time. These two sets represent two dimensions and should have a modulus of 1. This leads to the idea of $\cos(px)+i \sin(px)$ as describing a dynamic probability or wavefunction $W(x)$.

Link to Free Particle Action

The relativistic or nonrelativistic free particle action is $A = -Et + px$ if one treats t and x as independent. (This follows from both $-m_0 t \sqrt{1-v^2}$ and $.5m_0 t v^2$ with $v=x/t$). In the above analysis x and t are also kept separate. For example, for a fixed p linked to $m_1 v_1$ and $m_2 v_2$, the different frequencies associated with v_1 and v_2 (bouncing back and forth in the infinite well) are associated with E_1 and E_2 , but not with spatial density. For m_0 constant, p_1 and p_2 are associated with different frequencies (in time) due to v_1 and v_2 , but these are treated as different spatial densities i.e n_1 versus n_2 crests in L . We have noted previously that this $1/p$ length scale may also be obtained by considering px and noting that $x=1/p$ keeps it constant.

Time-Independent Spatial Density

In this note we have considered a particle in a square well and analysed a time-independent spatial density. Classically a particle first travels to the right and then to the left so what does it mean to have a spatial density? We argue that the notion of spatial density holds even in classical mechanics and in the literature (1) is given by $dt=C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity. Thus it is really a measure of the relative time dt spent in each constant dx length. In principle one may consider a spatial density for a quantum particle in an infinite well. We note that the notion of a classical spatial density bypasses the notion of frequency as a constant v_1 and v_2 with very different frequencies (same m_0) have the same spatial density. Thus we argue that the recipe $dt=C/v(x)$ may be good for describing relative motion, but seems to miss a fundamental aspect of the problem which appears in quantum mechanics, namely that one must bring in the notion of velocity frequency for different p same m_0 into the spatial density picture. This breaks the notion of relative motion defining spatial density yet on one hand there should be $P(x)=\text{constant}$.

As a result quantum mechanics has two sets of probabilities $W(x)$ a dynamical one and $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ a classical one. The dynamical one is based on crests and troughs and describes motion, but two distributions in two dimensions are needed to establish the direction of motion and ensure a modulus of 1. One may note that frequency i.e v_1 and v_2 for p_1 and p_2 (same m_0) is a dynamical feature which appears in the quantum $W(x)$, but disappears in the static classical $P(x)$.

Inteference

The idea of a set of crests and troughs describing a dynamical probability (i.e. $\cos(px)+i\sin(px)$) breaks the idea of a lack of information about x given by $P(x)$. $\cos(px)=1$ at $x=0$, $x=2\pi/\lambda$ so different x values are linked with different probabilities. Thus two free particles created at different origins would both have $P(x)=\text{constant}$, but at the dynamical level would have shifted probabilities that would add in an OR situation. This leads to the idea of interference.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that lack of information seems to play an important role in the structure of quantum mechanics. This lack of information in turn seems to be linked to measurement. Classically force and time may be measured. There is, however, a quantity "impulse" = $\int F dt$ which combines the two and is linked to change in p . Thus for the same impulse one may have $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2=m_3v_3$ etc. This leads to a lack of information of v the velocity which in turn represents a certain frequency within an infinite well of length L . Each v_1 , however, has the same impulse and so if spatial density is linked to impulse measurements, the same p should have the same distribution. Pressure on the walls is different due to velocity frequency, but this is a time feature, not a spatial one. Apparently spatial density is restricted to spatial considerations, not ones of frequencies which are not distinguished in a spatial probability measurement.

In the case of the same m_0 and p_1 and p_2 , there are also two different velocities and frequencies. Impulses are different and so these two are distinguished even spatially. If spatial probability density is considered to be time-independent this frequency needs to be displayed spatially i.e. one cannot throw out this important dynamical information as is done in the classical density $C/v(x) dx$ which only considers relative probabilities and is incomplete. As a result, one has a distribution with crests with base widths proportional to $1/p$. This is very different from a classical constant density for constant v , but experiment bears it out. The question is what should one do for a free particle? A set of crests does not show in which direction one has motion. Changing to a set of crests and troughs to create a kind of wave motion also does not show the direction of motion. Having two such probability distribution sets in two dimensions, however, does. If one wishes to link with $P(x)=\text{constant}$ for a free particle which should in some sense have no preference for one x versus another, then one may argue that the modulus should be 1. This leads to $\cos(px)+i\sin(px) = W(x)$.

References

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